

**THE CONFLICTS AND POSSIBLE RECONCILIATION
BETWEEN RUSSIA AND UKRAINE FROM THE
PERSPECTIVES OF ‘JUST WAR’ AND ‘TRANSITIONAL
JUSTICE’**

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Abstract

The Russia-Ukraine War has become one of the most widely studied and discussed war of modern times. This paper looks at the war from the perspectives of ‘Just War’ and ‘Transitional Justice’ and examines various aspects of it to analyze if it is justified from the viewpoint of Russia and Ukraine to fight this war. This paper concludes that Russia is wrong in its act of unprovoked aggression against Ukraine, while Ukraine, in its act of self-defence, is fighting a mostly just war. Furthermore, the paper also examines the possibilities of ‘Transitional Justice’ for the citizens of Ukraine, who suffer daily the threats of Russian aggression. It is concluded that though Ukraine has already begun the process of Transitional Justice with the help of various international organizations, the process, as usual, will span years or even decades.

Keywords: Russia-Ukraine War, Just War, Transitional Justice

Introduction

The root cause of the now infamous Russia-Ukraine conflict dates back to February 2014 when some disguised Russian troops covertly invaded Ukraine’s autonomous republic of Crimea, followed by the seizure of territories in Ukraine’s Donbas region (Ray, 2024) A full-scale invasion of Ukraine by Russia was launched on February 24, 2022, when Russian leader Vladimir Putin announced a “special military operation” in Ukraine at about 6 A.M. Moscow time. Leaders around the world stood in favor of Ukraine and promised severe sanctions against Russia. OCHR reported a total of 39,081 civilian casualties in Ukraine as of October 31, 2024, of which 12,162 people were reported injured (Department, 2024).

The main aim of this paper is to examine the Russia-Ukraine War in light of the Just War theory and discuss the possibilities of reconciliation between the two countries from the perspective of Transitional Justice. Here I argue that in an act of unprovoked aggression, Russia has waged a completely unjust war against Ukraine and left its counterpart with no option but to retaliate with all its strength and that Ukraine, in its act of self-defence is fighting a completely just war. Furthermore, in a quick discussion about transitional justice, I have argued that with no end in sight of the war, the fight for transitional justice will not be easy for Ukraine. Page 4 of this paper summarizes the result of Just War theory analysis.

The remainder of the paper has been divided into two broad sections. The first section explains the Just war theory and examines whether it is a just war from the perspectives of Russia and Ukraine, while the second section focuses on Transitional Justice.

What is a Just War theory?

Just War theory is a doctrine that revolves around the morality of war and talks about when and how a war should be fought (McMahan & McKim, 1993). After some revisionists questioned a few aspects of the theory, two types of it have come into existence. The original one is called the 'Traditional Just War Theory' and the revised version is better known as the 'Revisionist Just War Theory'. This paper, however, presents arguments in light of the Traditional Just War Theory, which consists of two sets of principles dealing with the permissibility of the resort to war, or *jus ad bellum* and permissible conduct in war, or *jus in bello*. Jeff McMahan and Robert McKim in their article, 'The Just War and The Gulf War' (McMahan & McKim, 1993) mention six principles of *Jus ad bellum* which include Just Cause, Proportionality, Last Resort, Reasonable Hope of Success, Competent Authority, and Right Intention, while the principles of *jus in bello* mentioned are Discrimination, Proportionality, and Minimal Force.

Going further, I will define the six principles of *Jus ad Bellum* (the discussion about *jus in bello* is not included in this paper due to word count restraint), and a study will be done from the viewpoint of Russia and Ukraine to conclude whether the war fought by both sides is a just war for both of them.

1. Just cause (JC)

McMahan and McKim talk about Just Aim and Just Cause (McMahan & McKim, 1993) which are important while understanding the morality of war. While Just Aim (hereafter JA) can be considered a goal so important that it is necessary to pursue war in order to achieve it, Just Cause (hereafter JC) is a goal or set of goals that provide the reason for going to war. In other words, a goal which permits the resort to war can be considered a JC.

Let us examine the causes considered by Russia and Ukraine to pursue this war and evaluate if they are justified enough to wage a war from their respective viewpoints.

Why did Russia wage the war?

A video posted by The Military Show on YouTube (Show, 2023) talks about the reasons which triggered an unprovoked assault by Russia on Ukraine. Apart from the “Russia and Ukraine are one and same country” (whose history goes back to the 10th century) rhetoric that Putin and his supporters might provide, ultimately, the real question comes down to security concerns.

Ukraine, throughout the 90s and after the fall out with the Soviet Union, transformed into a democracy and increasingly oriented towards the West. It was even eagerly trying to join the EU and in late November 2013, President Victor Yanukovich, a pro-Russian, signaled signing of an association agreement with the EU. However, he immediately withdrew after a meeting with Putin in Moscow, and it even appeared that Ukraine would join the Eurasian Economic Unit, a Russian-led organisation which would come into existence on January 1, 2015 (Ray, 2024). Russia also objected to Ukraine’s plan of joining the NATO when it was announced in 2008 as Putin did not appreciate the idea of a border sharing country joining a military alliance as strong and influential as NATO. In order to ensure Ukraine does not join the EU, Russia invaded Crimea – a Ukrainian autonomous Republic (Britannica, 2024) – in 2014, effectively preventing Ukraine from joining the NATO, as NATO rules provide for policy that does not allow countries engaged in active military conflict to join the organization. The move went on to become the main cause of the currently ongoing war.

In summary, it can be said that Russia’s main cause of waging this war is the security concern combined with its conflicted relations with the NATO. It has to be noted that NATO – an organization founded in part to counterbalance the Soviet Union expansion – is an alliance of 30 European countries and two North American countries, of which Ukraine is not one, among a very few other Eastern European countries; and in the event that Ukraine would have joined NATO, it would have been Kremlin’s “fundamental concern” (Jr., 2024).

Evaluating this main cause of Russia to wage a war which will soon complete its third anniversary in February, it can be justified from the viewpoint of Russia, as it concerns the security landscape of the country. Contrary to Jeff McMahan’s claim of Russian invasion of Ukraine being an unjust war (McMahan, 2024), I opine that though unprovoked, Russia had a sufficient enough JC to invade Ukraine as the country posed a credible threat to the future security of Russia. It is important here to note the difference between Russia’s ‘demand’ from Ukraine to not join the NATO and Russia’s strategic attempt to safeguard its future. While it is improper of Russia to dictate Ukraine to take some action in Russia’s favor, it is a moral duty of the country to do everything in its power to prioritize its safety and safeguard its interests, and it is from this logic that my opinion of Russia’s reason being justified in waging the war stem. Whether or not the technique - i.e., war in this case (and not diplomacy) - of safeguarding this interest is justified, is a question that requires more discussion and will be addressed later in this paper.

Ukraine, on its part, is also completely justified in fighting a war against Russia to defend its sovereign territory and fight for its people’s safety. Thus, Ukraine has a JC as well to fight the war.

	<u>Russia</u>	<u>Ukraine</u>
Just Cause	O	O
Proportionality	X	---
Last Resort	X	O
Competent Authority	X	O
Right Intention	X	O

Table 1: Summary of the Just War analysis

2. Proportionality and Last Resort

As described by Jeff McMahan, Proportionality (hereafter P) “holds that the relevant expected bad effects of war should not exceed the relevant expected good effects” (McMahan & McKim, 1993). Different authors might use different restrictions to measure these expected bad and good effects. Gregory Kavka, for example, says that to measure the proportionality of war, one must consider how the world would have been had the war not taken place (Kavka, 1991). However, as McMahan concludes – it will be difficult to determine how the situation would unfold had the war not occurred because different actors tend to have different alternatives – we, too will focus on the goods and evils involved only in the war and will evaluate whether or not bad effects of the actions taken by both sides so far will end with the end of war.

First and foremost, the threat of a nuclear attack given by Russia weakens its side significantly as the attack, if it occurs, will have its effect on future generations to come. In fact, Russian seizure of the Zaporizhzhia nuclear plant facility and the following fighting in the region has already raised concerns of a nuclear accident which even made International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) Director General, Rafael Mariano Grossi visit the place for an inspection (Action, 2024).

If Russia wants to pursue its just cause of preserving security in a morally acceptable way, it must abide by the ethics of war and attack only the military targets sparing noncombatants and defenseless civilians. However, Russia has grossly violated these ethics by targeting civilian areas in the Ukrainian capital, Kyiv and the total number of civilian deaths since the start of the war stands at 11,973 including 622 children (Release, 2024).

Another concern being voiced a lot in relation with Russia’s fight in the war is, ‘mass starvation’ caused by Russian attacks on Ukrainian ports. Ukraine is often called the ‘breadbasket of the world’ and is a major exporter of corn, wheat, and other vital organs. Just before the invasion, it was predicted to account for between 12% and 15% of global exports. This led to the spike in global wheat prices by about 28% just after the invasion, although they have considerably gone down since then (Show, 2023). To worsen Russia’s case even more, on July 17, 2023, it broke out of an agreement - signed with Ukraine in July 2022 - that allowed exports of agricultural products from Russian-controlled Ukrainian

Black Sea ports (Action, 2024), effectively reflecting that Russia does not care about the repercussions the war is having on people outside of the involved parties.

Ukraine's case for P has slightly become complicated since its advancement into the Russian territory, Kursk, and occupying around 35KMs taking 1150 square kilometers of the area under its control as of August 2024. Ukraine's JC until now for the war was self-defence. However, after its *invasion* of the Russian territory, the question is whether or not international law allows occupation of the enemy territory in response to a war of aggression. According to Chris O'Meara (O'Meara, 2024), temporary occupation of enemy's territory can be allowed only in exceptional cases of self-defence. Since, Ministry of Foreign Affairs gave a statement (MFA, 2024) that Ukraine "is not interested in taking over the territory in Kursk region of the Russian Federation, but wants to protect the lives of its people, in addition, the operation does not allow the enemy to transfer additional units to Donetsk region", it can be inferred that this was a necessary move on the part of Ukraine to deal with the ever-increasing aggression of Russia by bombing bridges in the region and creating a buffer zone inside Russia. Hence, as far as Ukraine occupies the region only temporarily and use it to neutralize the source of long-range missiles coming towards Ukraine, the provision of P will be satisfied.

Furthermore, there lies a probability, though little, of future NATO troops intervention in the support of Ukraine. However, if that happens, Russia has already warned of an "enormous danger" (Reuters, Russia warns of 'enormous danger' if NATO sends troops to Ukraine, 2024) in terms of a nuclear attack and that would defy the provision of P for Ukraine.

Considering the current scenario, however, Ukraine seems to be abiding with the P clause of the Just War theory.

Last Resort (hereafter LR) is another clause which evaluates the justification of a war. It "requires comparisons between the consequences of war and those of alternative means of achieving the JC" (McMahon & McKim, 1993) which ensures that all other peaceful means of solving the issues at hand should have been exhausted before resorting to the option of war for achieving one's JC. Russia, in this case has grossly violated the LR clause by invading Ukraine unprovoked.

Ukraine, on its part was left with no choice other than responding with force to safeguard its territory and people. As McMahan (McMahan, 2024) Responding with non-violence could have been an option on table for Ukraine, but that would have required years of training and preparation for the civilian population.

3. Reasonable Hope of Success is not evaluated in this paper because the evaluation of hope of success for the actors in a war can already be concluded from the discussions of P and LR.

4. Competent Authority and Right Intention

Just War theory also provides for the fulfillment of 'competent authority' clause which states that there should be a legitimate body - usually a state - to authorize the war and use of force. In the case of Russia-Ukraine War, Russia waged the war first but considering that Russia is an authoritative state with dictatorship, it is difficult to conclude that there is a competent authority who is authorizing the war.

For Ukraine though, a democratic State, the war is being led by Volodymyr Zelensky, a democratically elected President who came into power on May 20, 2019. Some might question his legality, as did Russia since his five-year term already got over in May 2024, he will continue to lead the country till the situation in Ukraine improves (Davlikanova, 2024).

The possession of Right Intention (hereafter RT), states that a war should be fought with a right intent and not for reasons involving self-interest. The interpretation of 'right intent' here is open to many and different versions, but generally, waging a war with the intent of fighting for country's good (freedom or peace for example) after weighing it against the economic and military consequences is considered a good intent (IEP, n.d.). While the case of Right Intention for Russia is significantly weak, as the war has kind of become a 'personal obsession' he is adamant on winning, for Ukraine, it is straightforward – self-defence – and has remained the same over all these years. Going forward, the complex change in Russia's intentions will be discussed in some detail.

It has been difficult for analysts to read Putin's mind regarding his intent of the war. However, it is widely accepted that he does not reminisce the collapse of the USSR and is largely critical of organizations like NATO

(Jr., 2024). Furthermore, as US Secretary of Defense Lloyd Austin put it, “the imperialistic policy of Russian Federation” (Austin, 2022) when it comes to Ukraine, reveal Putin’s difficulty in recognizing Ukraine’s independence, as he himself opines in a long essay that ethnic Ukrainians and ethnic Russians are all the same people who originally belonged to the Kievan Rus community (Putin, 2021). Thus, his personal resentment for NATO and his grievance towards the collapse of USSR combined with occupation of Ukraine’s territory based on history which dates back to the 10th century (when an East Slavic tribe occupied huge land from the Black Sea in the South to the Baltic Sea in the North but later merged into the Grand Duchy of Moscow. Ukraine, nevertheless, would become a separate state (Show, 2023) have been the sole motivators of Putin’s aggression, who wants to win the war at any cost.

To win this war and get what he wants, Putin has thrown in all his resources into the fight, despite an alarming number of Russian casualties on the frontline. As per one source, the average number of Russian deaths per day is 1500, with an estimated 115,000 to 160,000 Russian deaths since the war has started, while the total number of killed and wounded Russian casualties stands at 800,000 (Kovalev, 2024). This, despite the labor shortage, inflation and protests in Russia by mothers and wives of soldiers who against the long deployments of their sons and husbands (Crowley, 2024).

To top it all, Russia now deploys North Korean soldiers to fight this war for Kremlin, in addition to the hiring of private mercenary group – Wagner group – making the ‘personal obsession’ case against Putin even stronger. Thus, it is clear that the intentions of Putin in this war are not right.

Transitional Justice

Other than the criteria of *jus ad bellum* and *jus in bello* in the Just War theory, some scholar called for the inclusion of *jus post bellum*, a criterion that can deal with the morality of post-war settlements (Wikipedia, n.d.). The concept of Transitional Justice is only slightly different from *jus post bellum*. While the focus of *jus post bellum* is on ending the war and establishing peace, Transitional Justice aims for a ‘process’ that can lead to a less aggressive and more democratic establishment (May & Edenberg, 2013, p. 12).

A report released by the Secretary General of the United Nations in 2004 on the rule of law and transitional justice defined ‘Transitional Justice’ as:

The notion which comprises the full range of processes and mechanisms associated with a society's attempts to come to terms with a legacy of large-scale past abuses in order to ensure accountability, serve justice, and achieve reconciliation. These may include both judicial and non-judicial mechanisms, with differing levels of international involvement (or none at all) and individual prosecutions, reparations, truth-seeking, institutional reform, vetting and dismissals, or a combination thereof (General, 2004).

As mentioned in the starting of this paper, there exists a slight difference between *jus Post Bellum* concept of the Just War theory and the concept of Transitional Justice. A book titled, '*Jus Post Bellum* and Transitional Justice' discuss in detail these differences, while also explaining both the concepts. As per the book, the main principles of Transitional Justice include Rule of Law, Democracy, Truth, Forgiveness, and Punishment (Edenberg, p. 8). Going further, these principles are described briefly (as a detailed discussion is out of the range of this paper due to word constraint) and are based on the above-mentioned book (Edenberg L. M., pp. 8-11). Then we move on to a quick discussion about whether or not transitional justice is feasible in the case of Russia-Ukraine war.

The Rule of law deals with re-establishment of the system ensuring the laws are applied equally to all sections of the society, making 'fair application of laws' a central component of the transitional justice system.

The principle of Democracy deals with a transition from repressive regimes to democratic or less repressive regimes with the help of democratic institutions which ensure the civil and political rights of citizens are well preserved.

The principle of Truth deals with bringing the actions of perpetrators to the knowledge of public, ensuring the public is well aware of the details of past human rights violations.

Forgiveness is a highly controversial aspect of transitional justice, especially when it comes to the main oppressors and their hardline supporters. However, this principle is important for a transition from an unjust to a just system, and partial forgiveness, instead of complete forgiveness can be provided on prudential grounds, if required.

The last principle of Punishment, in complete contrast with the principle of forgiveness or amnesty, is also highly controversial. It talks about

appropriate forms of punitive measures to be applied on the perpetrators of violence while ensuring the smooth transition to a less atrocious system.

Keeping these in mind, possible reconciliation between Russia and Ukraine will not be quick. An already prolonged war, the peace is not in sight, though a lot depends on the US president-elect, Donald Trump after he will take over office on January 20, 2025. As of now, however, the war is nowhere near its end and possible outcomes include – a long continuation of the war, frozen conflict which will include an armistice stabilizing the front line where it is, a victory for Ukraine with the help of shift in Western policy, or ultimately a defeat for Ukraine where it surrenders and accepts Moscow's terms of settlement (Lough, 2024). No matter the results, the path of transitional justice between the two countries will not be easy.

For Ukraine, it has already begun the process of Transitional Justice (TJ) with the help of several international organizations, including the UN, Council of Europe and European Union, NGOs, independent observers, investigators, and media and the International Criminal Court (ICC) in the Hague had issued arrest warrant on March 17, 2023 for the Russian leader, Vladimir Putin and his Presidential Commissioner for Children's Rights, Maria Alekseyevna Lvova-Belova, as key perpetrators of war crimes and atrocities against Ukraine including abduction of Ukrainian children, unlawful transfer of people from areas in Eastern Europe to Russia, and unlawful deportation of population from Ukraine to Russia (Mihr, 2024). However, the process of serving this justice to Ukraine and its people can take long, lasting for decades even if the war comes to an end.

Conclusion

The aim of this paper was to examine the Russia-Ukraine war from the perspective of Just War theory and Transitional Justice. The paper has concluded that even if we consider Russia has genuine concerns of safety and assume it to be Moscow's JC for waging this war, it is fighting a highly unjustified war. Ukraine, on the other hand is trying to the best of its capabilities to defend the State and its fight in the war is completely justified.

Moreover, though Ukraine has already started the process of Transitional Justice, it is a long fight for the country against Russian aggression, with no end of war in sight.

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